

RQ3: How are OC and BM characteristics evaluated on DMM? v2

1. BM

- 1.1. Key Partners
 - 1.1.1. 001: Partner network for digitization.
 - 1.1.2. 008: Our vendor partners deliver value that enhances our digital competencies
 - 1.1.3. 024: The ecosystem is mature and it starts producing innovations that cross organizational boundaries.
 - 1.1.4. 024: Products and services developed and launched in partnership with ecosystem partners are leading the market and are based on data-driven customer knowledge shared across partner organizations.
 - 1.1.5. 024: The organization is developing new revenue streams and business models that incorporate ecosystem partners from inception through to launch and operation.
 - 1.1.6. 044: Integration of communication channels and collaboration with partners at high level.
 - 1.1.7. 044: IT security solutions are implemented for data exchange with business partners
 - 1.1.8. 044: Company has partnerships with lots of stakeholders and strategy is implemented or in implementation
 - 1.1.9. 051: The level of connectability and collaboration the organisation has with its suppliers is high; Customers have the ability to access the organisations systems to view manufacturing progress and delivery dates
 - 1.1.10. 051: There is evidence of partnering with external organisations related to deploying Industry
 - 1.1.11. 058: Fully digitised, integrated partner ecosystem with self-optimised, virtualised processes, focus on core competency
 - 1.1.12. 058: Near real-time access to extended set of operative information
 - 1.1.13. 058: decentralised autonomy.
 - 1.1.14. 062: (B)DA provider integrated (into the ecosystem)
 - 1.1.15. 117: We connect with our partners digitally. For example, we use modern business system integration platforms, such as API-enabled cloud-based services, to enable efficient business interactions that otherwise would not be possible.
 - 1.1.16. 117: My organisation fosters an integrated digital ecosystem. For example, we share data and/or provide integration points so that third parties can create value-add services that complement our own, increasing revenue and customer retention.
 - 1.1.17. 157: Do I have partners in the technology industry? What is the level of vertical integration? Are my digital concepts, methods and tools interconnected?
 - 1.1.18. 148: Do you have a digital environment that promotes growth within your company? - Identifying complementary digital partners - Integrating digital partners into the value chain to create added value - Systematically checking the overall benefit to the company - Ensuring continuing digital development
 - 1.1.19. 154: Does your company recognise and make use of the scope of its digital environment? - Driving forward digital networking - Establishing a digital infrastructure - Increasing automation to improve quality and efficiency
 - 1.1.20. 154: Can your company control the risks posed by close networking with the digital environment? - Preventing cyber-crime - Protecting IP and customers' data - Reducing counterparty risk
 - 1.1.21. 153: We are open to cooperating with our rivals and to competing with our partners
 - 1.1.22. 164: Most processes and interactions with external partners have been digitalized and a formal managerial process to monitor them is in place
 - 1.1.23. 153: We view our competition as broader than our current industry
- 1.2. Cost Structure
 - 1.2.1. 051: There is evidence that the organisation is investing in industry 4.0 technology and IT infrastructure;
 - 1.2.2. 055: Supply Chain contributes significantly to the value added margin with cost reductions
 - 1.2.3. 117: My organisation funds and resources digital transformation adequately.
 - 1.2.4. 117: Digital investment considers an organisation-wide approach (people and culture), rather than investing only in technology and/or developers.
 - 1.2.5. 148: My organization is investing in innovation capabilities to build new products and services through digital.
- 1.3. Key Resources
 - 1.3.1. 001: Insights derived from customer and interaction data
 - 1.3.2. 001: Expertise in big data used to develop new products.
 - 1.3.3. 020: We have an integrated view of key operational and customer information.
 - 1.3.4. 024: Machine learning and other advanced tools are being used to identify consumption trends and to develop new services and pricing strategies that are entirely new to the industry
 - 1.3.5. 024: Technologies such as advanced data analytics underpin innovation processes across the organization, from new service development through to service assurance to customer support.
 - 1.3.6. 024: Automation throughout the organization drives superior performance (e.g., speed, reliability, ARPU, NP5) compared to industry peers.
 - 1.3.7. 024: Tools using technology such as machine learning are implemented and used across the organization (and even to ecosystem partners) for predictive activities (e.g., service reliability, user consumption trends) that support digital business innovation.
 - 1.3.8. 037: Our IT-devices (e.g. notebook, tablet, mobile phone) are all connected.
 - 1.3.9. 037: Our systems are regularly brought to the latest level of digital technologies
 - 1.3.10. 044: Data usage in new product development is at high level
 - 1.3.11. 044: Triggering technologies (i.e. mobile and virtualization technologies, cloud) are in use
 - 1.3.12. 051: The organisation uses a 3DP machine for the creation of tooling, prototypes or spare parts; The organisation's 3DP machines use metal alloys as its raw material
 - 1.3.13. 051: The organisation store information within a cloud network; Hard resources (e.g. machines and robots) and softresources (e.g. data, documents and software) are connected to a cloud
 - 1.3.14. 051: The organisation uses advanced connectability technology between equipment, products and people; There is evidence that the organisation has embraced digitalisation for product, parts and machinery
 - 1.3.15. 051: The organisation has the ability to access data quickly and effectively from equipment, products, machines, facilities and systems; The organisation has the ability to analyse process data in order to make decisions, share information and improve negative trends;
 - 1.3.16. 051: There is evidence that the organisation is using sensors on products and supplied parts; Intelligent sensors are used within the organisation's manufacturing process to support automati
 - 1.3.17. 055: Cutting-edge and disruptive technologies are set up, and evolving
 - 1.3.18. 058: Central use of predictive analytics for real-time optimisation and automated event handling with intelligent database and self-learning algorithm enabling impact analysis and decision support
 - 1.3.19. 058: Single data lake with external data integration functionalities and flexible organisation. Partner service bus, secure data exchange
 - 1.3.20. 062: Smart product embedded in a (B)DA infrastructure
 - 1.3.21. 082: Digital multi-channel architecture enabling new sales and fostering the interaction with B2B and B2B2C customers
 - 1.3.22. 117: My organisation has the technological infrastructure and corresponding solutions in place to support real-time customer insights.
 - 1.3.23. 117: My organisation has systems, applications and tools in place that enable more efficient business processes
 - 1.3.24. 117: My organisation has the technological infrastructure and corresponding solutions in place to support real-time business decision making.
 - 1.3.25. 117: My organisation has services, systems, applications and tools in place in order to appropriately protect the organisation from cyber-attacks and other security risks.
 - 1.3.26. 117: My organisation has technology foundation in place that enables us to benefit from business networks and optimise collaboration with our suppliers.
 - 1.3.27. 157: Are my existing products and services digitalized?
 - 1.3.28. 157: Can I extend my portfolio with digital services or products?
 - 1.3.29. 117: My organisation has established an appropriate business intelligence system to help employees make timely decisions.
 - 1.3.30. 117: My organisation uses automated and integrated tools to support marketing and sales activities.
 - 1.3.31. 164: Comprehensive IT security solutions have been implemented for all relevant areas
- 1.4. Key Activities
 - 1.4.1. 001: Regular update of IT infrastructure.
 - 1.4.2. 001: Internal IT department ensures relevant digital technologies.
 - 1.4.3. 001: Customer data analyzed and acted upon in real time.
 - 1.4.4. 001: Digital expertise as core component in developing employees.
 - 1.4.5. 001: Data analysis results guide possible actions and strategic decisions.
 - 1.4.6. 008: We measure how channels work together to accomplish a desired outcome
 - 1.4.7. 008: We invest in targeted digital education and training at all levels of our organization
 - 1.4.8. 020: We are using digital technologies (such as analytics, social media, mobile, and embedded devices) to understand our customers better.
 - 1.4.9. 020: We use analytics to make better operational decisions.
 - 1.4.10. 024: The organization is breaking new ground in the way it innovates, establishing innovation processes that are new to the industry.
 - 1.4.11. 024: New digital services launched in the last 3 years account for a significant share of total digital revenues (e.g., >30%)
 - 1.4.12. 037: Collected data are checked for completeness and relevance regularly
 - 1.4.13. 037: During the production of a product data are collected and these data are made available to subsequent activities
 - 1.4.14. 037: Based on the collected data digital services are offered
 - 1.4.15. 082: Total data integration is neither required nor reasonable, business groups should rather integrate separate data pools
 - 1.4.16. 117: My organisation actively and regularly assesses technical, business and social risk factors when it comes to technology investment.
 - 1.4.17. 117: My organisation considers the scalability of digital infrastructure to meet the demand driven by marketing, promotions or legislation requirements.
 - 1.4.18. 117: The degree of risk mitigation in a project is varied according to the assessed risk level of the project.
 - 1.4.19. 117: My organisation is data focused and uses data for environmental sensing/machine learning/predictive analysis
 - 1.4.20. 117: My organisation uses technology to deliver more efficient business outcomes, for example by using process automation and hardware virtualisation, cutting out the intermediaries or using data to become more accurate and predictive
 - 1.4.21. 148: My organization is adequately preparing for disruptions projected to occur in my industry due to digital trends
 - 1.4.22. 153: We manage our data as a strategic asset we are building over time.
 - 1.4.23. 153: Our data strategy is focused on how to turn data into new value
 - 1.4.24. 153: Our data is organized to be accessible by all divisions of the company
 - 1.4.25. 164: We systematically adapt our business models or create new ones for digital-enabled growth, including customer segments, channels, activities/resources and the value proposition
 - 1.4.26. 164: Effective technology planning, deployment, integration and use to support the digital-enabled business.
- 1.5. Value Propositions
 - 1.5.1. 001: Customers included in the development of new product ideas
 - 1.5.2. 001: Customer testing to improve digital products.
 - 1.5.3. 001: Digital content designed according to individual user situation.
 - 1.5.4. 001: Customer experience is consistent across all channels
 - 1.5.5. 008: Customer insights inform digital design and development
 - 1.5.6. 020: We use digital technologies to increase the performance or added-value of our existing products and services.
 - 1.5.7. 001: Product and service expansion with digital services
 - 1.5.8. 024: Dynamic pricing is being used to maximize customer value through full personalisation and flexibility.
 - 1.5.9. 024: New (including non-traditional telecommunication) digital services are being developed based on deep knowledge of customer log., advanced analytic) and are, from inception, fully integrated across all touch points (e.g., one screen/app/bill for all services).
 - 1.5.10. 044: Company offer service insights for its business, customers and partners according to data obtained from the product improvements
 - 1.5.11. 044: In after sales services process, company benefits from lots of data and offer services in wide range
 - 1.5.12. 044: Campaign systems and sales channels has high level integration and data analytics tools are in use to measure campaign performances
 - 1.5.13. 051: The organisation has the ability to quickly and easily customise products to a customer's request whilst maintaining the same service quality
 - 1.5.14. 058: Integrated Customer Journey
 - 1.5.15. 062: Services based on (B)DA ("data as a service")
 - 1.5.16. 082: New customer experience through virtual reality products or fully connected dispensing tools
 - 1.5.17. 082: Content marketing, more personalization, and new digital customer touch points based on customer insights
 - 1.5.18. 082: Enhancing established products with sensors and connectivity, making them smart (e.g., dispensing tools)
 - 1.5.19. 082: Offering smart services based on smart products, such as remote operation of dispensing tools
 - 1.5.20. 082: Individualizing services based on customer needs through data analysis
 - 1.5.21. 117: My customers can effectively communicate with my organisation to co-create value.
 - 1.5.22. 117: My supplier can effectively communicate with my organisation to co-create value.
 - 1.5.23. 153: Our value proposition is defined by changing customer needs
 - 1.5.24. 117: My organisation's digital initiatives are currently generating value (e.g. new lines of revenue) and/or efficiencies (e.g. cost reductions), and the impacts are increasing over time
 - 1.5.25. 117: There are very few technical issues in the delivery of our digital services.
 - 1.5.26. 117: When technical issues do occur in service delivery, we are able to resolve them within an acceptable period of time (i.e. within customer expectations of our industry).
 - 1.5.27. 117: My organisation's digital initiatives are currently generating value (e.g. new lines of revenue) and/or efficiencies (e.g. cost reductions), and the impacts are increasing over time.
 - 1.5.28. 153: We look to create value through platforms and external networks
 - 1.5.29. 153: We are focused on our customers' changing digital habits and path to purchase
- 1.6. Customer Segments
 - 1.6.1. 058: Management across all digital marketing and sales channels with customer empathy and CRM
 - 1.6.2. 172: We have analyzed our customer base and divided it into multiple segments.
 - 1.6.3. 164: There is genuine and systematic understanding of how each of our customer segments are changing in the digital environment, what their needs are, and how to address them
- 1.7. Customer Relationships
 - 1.7.1. 153: Our customers' advocacy is the biggest influence on our brand and reputation
 - 1.7.2. 153: We use marketing to attract, engage, inspire, and collaborate with customers
- 1.8. Channels
 - 1.8.1. 001: Personalized digital customer communication.
 - 1.8.2. 001: Customer interaction via both traditional and digital channels
 - 1.8.3. 020: We use digital channels (such as online, social media, and mobile) to market our products and services
 - 1.8.4. 020: We sell our products and services through digital channels.
 - 1.8.5. 020: We use digital channels to provide customer service

1.8.6. 164: Our firm has a broad and integrated digital presence across several media through different digital activities. We regularly measure the impact of our digital market presence

1.8.7. 164: The firm successfully interacts with (potential) customers and delivers customer service across multiple digital channels

1.9. Revenue Streams

1.9.1. 044: Analytics studies are conducted and data obtained from environment is used in product pricing and dynamic pricing

1.9.2. 044: Existing products and services are compatible with digital business models which is supported with resources at high level "As a service" has been implemented and is being offered.

1.9.3. 044: Revenue is generated from data-driven services (over 10%)

1.9.4. 164: An important part of revenues is generated by data-driven (online) services (% of revenues)

2. OC

2.1. Digital Technologies

2.1.1. 001: Employees are familiar with digital products.

2.1.2. 008: We use digital tools to promote employee innovation, collaboration, and mobility

2.1.3. 037: Employees can exchange information and communicate with each other via collaboration platforms.

2.1.4. 055: Systems, machines, people are holistically connect and process fully digitalized

2.1.5. 117: Digital technology is an essential element of realising the vision of my organisation.

2.1.6. 117: My organisation utilises digital to reach its full potential in the market (local, national or global) by creating new ways to connect with customers.

2.1.7. 117: Everyone in the organisation knows of, understands and is able to act on our digital strategy.

2.1.8. 117: Technology is no longer a bottleneck in our organisation. For example, our technical delivery teams can implement services faster than we can generate new service delivery ideas.

2.1.9. 154: Facilitating situational workplace design?

2.1.10. 024: Tools using technology such as machine learning are implemented and used across the organization (and even to ecosystem partners) for predictive activities (e.g., service reliability, user consumption trends) that support digital business innovation.

2.2. Data-driven decision making

2.2.1. 037: Every employee has access to the data relevant to his/her work

2.2.2. 051: The organisation operate using zero paper to control, display and transport data

2.2.3. 082: Strict data ownership and privacy policy due to sensitive customers and critical intellectual property

2.2.4. 082: Data security is of high priority as industrial cyberattacks are perceived as a serious threat and need to be monitored

2.2.5. 148: How would you characterize your organization's decision making on the following scale?

2.3. Knowledge sharing

2.3.1. 001: Internal IT department provides advice to the other departments

2.3.2. 117: Employees regularly work in interdisciplinary teams and are supported in cross-skilling and knowledge sharing.

2.3.3. 148: Our employees have sufficient knowledge and ability to execute our organization's digital strategy

2.4. Sharing assets

2.5. Organizational learning

2.5.1. 117: My organisation continuously invests in developing digital skills of employees

2.5.2. 008: We invest in targeted digital education and training at all levels of our organization

2.5.3. 148: My organization provides me and my coworkers with the resources or opportunities to develop skills to thrive in a digital environment

2.5.4. 148: I expect my organization to help me develop skills to thrive in a digital environment

2.5.5. 154: Do your employees have the skills to meet customers' needs efficiently and effectively? - Mentoring - Increasing employee diversity - Coordinating skills development and experience with soft skills - Combining experience with potential

2.5.6. 154: Are your employees' skills developing as rapidly as market needs?

2.5.7. 154: Are your employees' skills developing as rapidly as market needs? - Making use of talent management - Developing new approaches to initial and continuing training - Creating a mindset of curiosity

2.5.8. 154: Encouraging lifelong learning?

2.5.9. 164: Employees possess all necessary digital skills, which are updated regularly through a formal learning and development programme

2.5.10. 024: Initial investments are being made to develop digital competencies, including training programmes.

2.5.11. 024: The need for digital competencies has been identified and a general development plan is being defined.

2.5.12. 024: Recruitment of select "experts" to bring needed skills is ongoing, often in isolated teams.

2.6. Innovation

2.6.1. 001: New digital business ideas or business model implemented.

2.6.2. 001: Suitable conditions for developing digital innovations.

2.6.3. 001: Digital innovation even when financially risky

2.6.4. 001: Failed digital projects are communicated in a proactive manner.

2.6.5. 001: Readiness to take risks with existing business

2.6.6. 001: Digital product creation across all departments and functions.

2.6.7. 001: Test and modify new products using prototypes.

2.6.8. 001: Our employees regularly contribute ideas for digital products.

2.6.9. 001: Evaluate errors in order to improve.

2.6.10. 008: We take measured risks in order to enable innovation

2.6.11. 020: We have launched new business models based on digital technologies

2.6.12. 051: There is a sense of continuous improvement culture within the company

2.6.13. 062: Understanding of data as an important value carrier

2.6.14. 078: Rewarding for successful initiatives

2.6.15. 078: Systematically evaluating and supporting digital initiatives

2.6.16. 117: In my organisation everyone has a mandate to think creatively and innovate.

2.6.17. 117: My organisation takes a rigorous and systematic approach to innovation or change management.

2.6.18. 117: My organisation conducts both small iterative experiments, and enterprise wide initiatives to realise innovation that has business impact.

2.6.19. 117: My organisation conducts innovation activities as a regular task.

2.6.20. 148: To what extent do you agree that the following are objective(s) of your organization's digital strategy: Increase innovation?

2.6.21. 148: My organization is actively implementing initiatives to change its culture to be more collaborative, risk embracing, and agile in response to digital trends?

2.6.22. 154: Do these cultural values support you in making use of your employees' creative and entrepreneurial skills? - Promoting ownership and autonomy - Creating spaces for creativity and experimentation - Facilitating continuous experimentation / fail forward

2.6.23. 117: My organisation has embedded a proactive risk management approach within the culture and processes of the organisation.

2.6.24. 153: We make decisions through experiments and testing wherever possible

2.6.25. 153: We innovate in rapid cycles, using prototypes to learn quickly

2.6.26. 153: We are able to seed and develop new ideas that are unusual for our business

2.6.27. 164: Our company takes a systematic and proactive approach to technology-driven product/service innovation in the digital environment

2.6.28. 164: We practice a systematic and proactive open innovation approach: invite customers/potential clients to provide feedback and ideas via digital platforms (Crowdsourcing), we collaborate intensively with further external sources such as providers and universities

2.6.29. 164: We have a consistent digitally enabled innovation and growth strategy in alignment with our resources

2.6.30. 024: The organization is developing a strategy for digital innovation across functions.

2.6.31. 024: A digital innovation strategy has been developed with focus on agile development and open a data-driven innovation processes

2.6.32. 024: Open innovation with external parties including partners, user, and others has been implemented to support digital innovation.

2.6.33. 024: Collaboration with other ecosystem partners is well established, generating service innovation that is ahead of competition.

2.6.34. 024: The organization is focused on digital innovation.

2.6.35. 024: The organization is breaking new ground in the way it innovates, establishing innovation processes that are new to the industry

2.6.36. 024: The organization is recognized in the industry as leader in digital innovation.

2.6.37. 024: New digital services launched in the last 3 years account for a significant share of total digital revenues (e.g., >30%)

2.7. Collaboration

2.7.1. 001: External experts involved to develop knowledge of digitization.

2.7.2. 001: Promotion of flexible, mobile work.

2.7.3. 001: Internal experts on digital topics act as contact persons.

2.7.4. 001: Tools with videoconferencing and screen sharing

2.7.5. 001: Digital platforms to cooperate with internal and external partners.

2.7.6. 001: Standardized, efficient procedures for cooperation with partners

2.7.7. 008: Our marketing and technology resources work together to co-create our digital technology road map

2.7.8. 008: Our organization model encourages cross-functional collaboration

2.7.9. 020: Digital initiatives are coordinated across silos such as functions or regions

2.7.10. 020: IT and business leaders work together as partners

2.7.11. 044: Departments are open to cross-company collaboration to drive improvements

2.7.12. 058: Collaboration as a key value driver

2.7.13. 078: Fostering collaboration & preventing siloing

2.7.14. 117: Employees regularly work in interdisciplinary teams and are supported in cross-skilling and knowledge sharing.

2.7.15. 117: Teams work collaboratively on projects and share developments all the way through, factoring in feedback and new insights to improve as they go.

2.7.16. 148: My organization is actively implementing initiatives to change its culture to be more collaborative, risk embracing, and agile in response to digital trends?

2.8. Customer Centricity

2.8.1. 008: We use customer-centric metrics like Net Promoter Score or lifetime value to measure success

2.8.2. 008: We use customer experience assets, like personas and journey maps, to steer our technology design

2.8.3. 008: We prioritize overall customer experience over the performance of any individual channel

2.8.4. 117: User Experience research is conducted by my organisation to better understand customer pain points as part of designing better products and services.

2.8.5. 117: My organisation has the ability to design and deliver a tailored product to fulfil customers' needs.

2.8.6. 117: My organisation is customer centric and creates digital value by addressing customers' problem in a new and innovative way.

2.8.7. 117: My organisation has the ability to design and deliver a tailored product to fulfil customers' needs.

2.8.8. 117: My organisation provides customers with a fully integrated experience in all areas of interaction including technology and brand.

2.8.9. 117: My organisation continuously improves its digital and physical experiences to deliver genuine value to the customer.

2.8.10. 117: My customers can effectively communicate with my organisation to address complaints and help resolve issues.

2.8.11. 117: My organisation has a proven ability to identify customer's latent needs.

2.8.12. 117: My organisation has demonstrated ability to pivot its purpose, products and service based on analysis of customer insight and key performance metrics.

2.8.13. 148: To what extent do you agree that the following are objective(s) of your organization's digital strategy: Improve customer experience and engagement?

2.8.14. 153: Our first priority is creating value for customers

2.9. Empowerment

2.9.1. 020: There are possibilities for everyone in the company to take part in the conversation around digital transformation

2.9.2. 037: Responsibilities concerning digital plans are clearly assigned

2.9.3. 117: My organisation empowers staff to work autonomously as required, while providing an appropriate level of vision, guidance and coordination to maintains focus.

2.9.4. 117: Employees feel empowered and take calculated risks to be successful.

2.9.5. 154: Creating trust?

2.9.6. 154: Defining clear basic values

2.9.7. 164: Employees are fully empowered to experiment with digital initiatives and implement them

2.9.8. 164: Everyone in the firm shares an understanding of our digital vision and has favourable attitudes and behaviours towards digitalization

2.10. Agility and Flexibility

2.10.1. 001: Adjust our digital services at short notice.

2.10.2. 001: Able to react quickly to changes.

2.10.3. 001: Connect systems quickly to other services via open interfaces.

2.10.4. 001: "Early warning" system to identify relevant technologies

2.10.5. 001: Pursue digital innovations alongside usual business operations.

2.10.6. 008: We leverage modern architectures (APIs, cloud, etc.) to promote speed and flexibility

2.10.7. 008: Our technology budget is fluid to allow for shifting priorities

2.10.8. 055: Outstanding responsiveness and flexibility

2.10.9. 082: Organizational agility through e.g. agile project

2.10.10. 174: has a common vision across the company, so the workforce knows what overall goal they are contributing to

2.10.11. 174: has a flat structure and an empowered workforce, enabling rapid decision-making and more engaged employees

2.10.12. 174: is transparent and has standardized processes with clear output

2.10.13. 174: is capable of bringing innovation to market quickly

2.10.14. 174: is not held back by legacy systems and tools. Its IT landscape should also be capable of supporting the required changes

2.10.15. 117: Employees quickly recover from setbacks and reframe their approach.

2.10.16. 117: Efficient and agile processes and systems are used to react to rapid business change.

2.10.17. 148: How would you characterize your organization's agility on the following scale?

2.10.18. 117: Employees are able to quickly identify the core of a business or customer problem, and self-organise to address the solution timely manner.

2.10.19. 154: Is your organisation able to react rapidly to changing market conditions (agility and flexibility)? - Introducing flat hierarchies - Reducing complexity - Developing anticipatory planning systems

2.10.20. 153: We aim to adapt early to stay ahead of the curve of change.

2.10.21. 164: The organization has adopted agile methodologies to develop digital initiatives and this is managed based on a structured method

2.10.22. 024: The organization is flexible and easily adapts to changes in the market in a more agile way than competitors.

2.11. Openness towards change

2.11.1. 001: New digital business ideas or business model implemented

2.11.2. 037: The company culture shows openness on all levels when it comes to new digital technologies.

2.11.3. 037: The company culture is open on all levels to accept new digital technologies

2.11.4. 037: Our employees embrace the change towards digitization and perceive it as a chance

2.11.5. 051: There is evidence to suggest the majority of the work-force is familiar with the Industry 4.0

2.11.6. 117: My organisation has the process in place to understand and learn from a failure.

2.11.7. 117: Employees feel empowered and take calculated risks to be successful.

2.11.8. 154: Creating a mindset of change

2.11.9. 153: We accept failure in new ventures but look to reduce cost and increase learning

2.12. Leadership

2.12.1. 117: Leaders in my organisation have a compelling long-term goal for my organisation

2.12.2. 117: Leaders in my organisation have the ability to communicate their future foresight throughout the organisation.

2.12.3. 117: Leaders in my organisation actively identify and realise opportunities for digital enabled business growth

2.12.4. 117: Leaders in my organisation have empowered employees to work in cross-functional teams and collaborative environments

2.12.5. 148: Our organization's leadership has sufficient knowledge and ability to lead our organization's digital strategy

2.12.6. 148: How would you characterize your organization's leadership structure on the following scale?

2.12.7. 024: The organization has articulated the need for digital transformation.

2.12.8. 024: The organization has a vision for digital transformation, which begins to drive change towards a digitally-savvy workforce

2.12.9. 024: Management is continuously communicating the digital strategy and advances in its implementation across the whole organization.